

Awareness of Patients about Dental Implants as Treatment Modality of Missing Tooth Among Patients Visiting Government Medical College in Madhepura

Ahtasham Anwar¹, Shagufta Syreen², Bimleshwar Kumar³

¹Assistant Professor Department of Dentistry, Jannayak Karpoori Thakur Medical College and Hospital, Madhepura, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India.

³Ex Associate Professor, Department of Dentistry, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India.

Received: 06-05-2021 / Revised: 11-06-2021 / Accepted: 29-07-2021

Corresponding author: Dr. Shagufta Syreen

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Loss of tooth is quite common among general population and it is due to various reasons either due to caries, or trauma or developmental. With the advancement of technology and aesthetic consideration of patients increasing no of patients opt for dental implant as prosthesis for lost tooth. **Materials and Methods:** Surveys of 100 patients were conducted among patients visiting the government medical college, Madhepura for rehabilitation of lost tooth. This is questionnaires based survey provided in Hindi as well as English for better understanding. **Results:** Out of 100 patients surveyed only 29% of patient knows about dental implant however 67% knows that missing tooth is replaced where as Only 13% knows that missing tooth is replaced with dental implant and only 9% aware that dental implant is placed in jaw bone. However 46% wants dental implant if cost is low. **Conclusion:** there is need of improving education and socioeconomic condition of masses to understand the restoration of lost dental structure. First of all we have to educate about importance of dental and oral structure. Continuing education programs for dentist practicing in peripheral areas and small town is necessary. Dental education and implants advantages must be in local dialect for better understanding.

Keywords: RPD, FPD, CD, Dental Implants

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The aims and objective of any prosthetic treatment is to rehabilitate the patient to the

normal so that normal function should be carried out and it's also improved patient aesthetics, speech and other relevant

function. With the advancement in science and technology multiple options are in patient hands to replace missing tooth in form of removable partial or complete denture, fixed partial denture or in form of dental implants. Various literature on dental implants suggests that majority of patients treated with implant-supported prosthesis have reported improvement in their quality of life and self-confidence, along with psychological benefits[1].

Treatment of lost tooth by removable partial or complete denture is less reasonable due to various factors viz anatomical, psychological, physiological and other functional factors and it has less retentive and stability which affect masticatory ability of the patient especially in lower jaw[2]. Implant treatment comes into limelight because of it provides long term result by increasing retention, stability, functional efficiency and quality of life[3]. According to Pommer et al, in Austria, over course of five years a significant increase in implant treatment, again in another survey in 2008, 79% of patients express desire for implant treatment in comparison of 56% in first survey[4]. The number of dental implants

inserted annually worldwide has been estimated to be I million. Complete information is required to do implant and to guide the patient in choice of most feasible option[5].

Aims And Objectives:

To know the level of awareness among patients for dental implant as treatment option.

Material and Methods:

A questionnaire-based survey is taken in govt medical college, Madhepura among patients coming in dental OPD for the treatment of lost tooth. Ethical permission is taken for the study. The aims and objectives of the study were explained to the subject and written consent was taken, however those not willing to give consent were excluded.

A total of 100 patients were taken for the study and provided the printed questionnaire consisting of 10 questions with the intent of evaluating the awareness of dental implant as a treatment option. The question is provided in English and Hindi (local language) for better understanding.

QUESTIONNAIRE:

1. Have you heard about dental implant?

a) Yes 29 b) No 71

2. do you know that lost/missing tooth is replaced?

A) Yes 67 b) No 19 c) Not known 14

3.do you know the various modes of replacement of lost/missing tooth.

a) RPD 43 b) FPD 22 c) CD 26 d) IMPLANT 09

4)do you know the most common method of replacement of lost tooth?

a) RPD b) FPD C) CD d) Implant

5.do you know about dental implant is used for lost/missing tooth replacement.

a) Yes 13 b) No 87

6.what is the means of knowing about dental implant.

a) Form dentist 87 b) From known person 10 c) From tv or other means 3

7.do you know the advantages and disadvantages associate with dental implant treatment.

a) Yes 7 b) No 93

8. do you know where implants is placed.

a) Jawbone 9 b) Inside gums 17 c) Not know 74

9. do you know the cost of dental implants.

a) Yes 7 b) No 88 c) Little bit 5

10. do you want implant as treatment if other options are available.

a) Yes, if cost is low 46 b) No 34

Results:

A Total of 100 patients coming for dental treatment were taken for the study and all the necessary parameters were explained in their local language. A written questionnaire was provided to all.

In this present study it was found that majority of population did not know about dental implant whereas only 29% out of 100 knew about dental implant.

A total of 67% know that missing tooth is replaced whereas 19% of patients are unaware about missing tooth replacement with either FPD, RPD OR CD.

Regarding mode of replacement of missing tooth 43% of patient says that RPD is commonest mode of replacement where as FPD accounts to 22%, however in terms of implant it is only 9%.

In this study it is found that only 13% of patients know about dental implant is used for missing or lost tooth replacement.

In the present study it is found that knowledge of dental implant mostly comes from treating dentist. Only 3% of patients knew it from TV or other means.

In this study most of the patients 93% of them has no knowledge of advantages and disadvantages of dental implant.

In this study most of the patients 74% are not aware about site of placement of dental implant, only 7% knew that it is placed inside jawbone.

Majority of respondent in the study were not aware of cost of dental implant which is

88%, only 7% has some knowledge of cost of dental implant.

Most of the respondent i.e 46% is ready to avail treatment if cost of implant is low. whereas 34% of respondent is not willing dental implant as treatment option due to other reasons.

Discussion:

With the increasing awareness of replacing missing tooth with the structure that works like a natural tooth dental implant gained a momentum. it is the forefront of clinical practice for a decade and half now. dental implant has good success rate which makes it good choice for replacing lost and missing tooth[6]. About a one million implant are inserted each year worldwide which shows its success and acceptance among patients. However due to lack of knowledge and paucity of knowledge regarding dental implant in most of developing nation less people are opting for the treatment.

In the present survey it is seen that only 29% of the respondents are aware of dental implants which is very low in compared to the survey conducted by Zimmer et al in 1992 is 77% and Berge 70.1% in 2000 and Tepper et al 72% in 2003. this is due to low education level and backwardness of this region.

In the present study about 67% of patients knew that missing tooth is replaced, it means that rest of the patient is not even aware about that missing is replaced with prostheses.

Regarding mode of replacement of lost or missing tooth 43% knows about removable partial denture, implants Only 9%, fixed partial denture 22%. This is due to poor socioeconomic condition and lack of education in this region.

Regarding knowledge about dental implants as a replacement of missing tooth only 13% patient heard about it which is very low in comparison to big and developed cities.

Regarding advantage and disadvantage of implant only 7% is aware about that and rest of the patient were not aware about it.

Regarding placement of implant only 9% knows that it is placed inside jawbone which shows lack of knowledge and backwardness of the region.

In this survey it was found that only 7% knows about cost of dental implants and 46% says that they want implant as replacement of missing tooth if cost is low.

Conclusion:

There is need of improving education and socioeconomic condition to improve general awareness about dental treatment and in particular dental implant.

Continuing dental education programme in large scale to train small town dentist to various aspects of dental implant is needed so they easily convey to patients about various benefits of dental implant treatment.

References:

1. Kohli S, Bhatia S, Kaur A, Rathakrishnan T. Public knowledge and acceptance of dental implant treatment in Malaysian population. *J Interdiscipl Dent.* 2014; 4:76–80.
2. Balsi TJ, Wolfinger GJ, Hernandez RE. Patient attitude before and after dental implant rehabilitation. *Implant dent* 1994; 3:106-9.
3. NU Zitzmann, P Sendi, CP Marinello. An economic evaluation of implant

treatment in edentulous patients-preliminary results. *Int J Prosthodont.* 2005;18(1):20-27.

4. Pommer B, Zechner W, Watzak G, Ulm C, Tepper G. Progress and trends in patient's mindset on dental implants. I: level of information, sources of information and need for patient information. *Clin Oral Implants Res* 2011 Feb;22(2);223-229.
5. GH Guyatt, DJ Cook, Health status, quality of life, and the individual. *J Am Med Assoc.* 1994;272(8):630-31.
6. Zimmer CM, Zimmer WM, Williams J, Liesener J. public awareness and acceptance of dental implants. *Int J oral Maxillofac Implants* 1992;7(2): 228-32